

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMS OF EXTRACURRICULAR WORK OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF MASTER'S STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problem of improving the organization of Master's students' independent work in foreign language in higher education. In the conditions of multilevel education, Master's students are subjected to high requirements in the field of language training, in particular, to conduct their research work. However, the authors emphasize the insufficient disclosure of the content of independent work at the master's stage, which is mainly reduced to control. The article defines the concept of independent work, lists its forms, and emphasises its role in the formation of professional-communicative skills. The authors suggest that the peculiarity of the organization of independent work of master's students in foreign language is in the profile preparation for future professional, scientific and research activities. The authors give an example of a specific methodology of work with master's students of the Faculty of Philology. The experimental methodology confirms the authors' conclusion about the effectiveness of the organization of independent work with the emphasis on the research approach, proves the increase of motivation in Master's students and the development of skills in working with foreign-language information.

Keywords: self-education; independent work; communicative competence; professional-oriented approach; motivation; master's training; research approach; individualization; interaction

The main purpose of extracurricular independent work of a master's student is to consolidate and systematize theoretical knowledge obtained during lectures, to form skills and abilities and to master the experience of creative and research activity. This type of independent work contributes to the development of independence, responsibility and organization, creative approach to solving problems of educational and professional levels [1]. Extracurricular independent work is compulsory for each master.

Extracurricular independent work of the master in the process of mastering the discipline includes:

- for mastering knowledge: reading the text (textbook, primary source, additional literature); drawing up a text plan; graphic representation of the text structure; text outlining; extracts from the text; work with dictionaries and reference books; familiarisation with normative documents; educational and research work; use of audio and video recordings, computer equipment and the Internet, etc.;

- to consolidate and systematise knowledge: work with the lecture notes; work on the study material (textbook, primary source, additional literature, audio and video recordings); drawing up a plan and theses of the answer; drawing up tables to systematise the study material; studying normative materials; answering control questions; analytical processing of the text (annotating, reviewing, abstracting, etc.); preparation of theses of messages for presentation at a seminar, conference; preparation of essays, reports: drawing up a bibliography, etc.;

- for the formation of skills: solving tasks and exercises according to the sample; solving variant tasks and exercises; performing graphs, schemes; performing calculation and graphic works; solving situational production (professional) tasks; preparing for business

games; designing and modelling different types and components of professional activity; preparing term papers and creative works (essays).

The forms and methods of control over the independent work of master's students include testing, control works, defence of creative works, etc. [2]. The criteria for assessing the results of the independent work of a master's student are:

- level of mastery of the training material,
- ability to use theoretical knowledge when performing practical tasks,
- completeness of general academic ideas, knowledge and skills on the studied topic, to which this independent work is related,
- validity and clarity of the answer to the question posed on the extracurricular independent work,
- design of the reporting material in accordance with the requirements for such materials known or set by the teacher.

The principle of the Bologna system is based on the organization of students' independent work, on increasing their personal responsibility and contribution, as well as on constant control over the progress of learning, with independent work being defined as individual or collective learning activities carried out without the direct guidance of the teacher, but on his/her assignments and under his/her control. Independent work is the most important form of educational process organization, so it is necessary to focus students' attention on "its direct influence on the formation of such parameters of qualification characteristics as mobility, ability to predict the situation and actively influence it, independence of assessments, etc. so that students see the positive results of their work, and that the experienced success contributes to the transformation of mediated

interest into direct interest" [3, p. 111]. The organization of independent work as an integral part of the learning process has always been and remains obligatory in the course of foreign language teaching. This means that in order to achieve practical learning objectives (in a non-language university it is the formation of graduates' general cultural and communicative professionally oriented competences in accordance with the curriculum of the discipline, the formation of their self-education skills, etc.) the teacher should integrate all types of learning activities with independent work [4, p. 43]. At the same time, this means that the successful achievement of the goals of foreign language teaching requires continuous improvement of the ways of organizing each type of learning activity that takes place in the study of a foreign language, including the improvement of the organization of such an obligatory type of learning activity as independent work. The problems of organizing independent work in the study of various disciplines, including the discipline of "Foreign Language", have always attracted the attention of psychologists, teachers and methodologists. Analysis of the literature of the 20th-21st centuries shows a gradual comprehensive perception of the concept of independent work. Thus, for example, in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, the issues related to the definition of the concept of "independent work", its types, ways of organization and the possibility of using various technical means in the mode of independent work were considered in detail. [5; 6]. In the 90s of the XX century, scientists noted that it is independent work that increases students' motivation, causes a conscious attitude to learning, and also develops such personal qualities and properties as organization, independence, self-control and others [4, p. 45]. At the end of the last century and at the beginning of the new one, psychological and methodological studies of various issues of organization and management of independent work in a foreign language continued. Researchers paid special attention to the individual approach to learning in universities, the development of students' personality and the use of modern information technologies [4, p. 45]. In the system of professional education, a special place is occupied by multilevel training, in which Master's degree is the second stage of higher education.

Master's training is characterized by an increase in the share of independent work of Master's students, and its organization is influenced by many factors, including new specialties and the introduction of modular programs. Foreign language teaching in higher education is professionally oriented, so foreign language skills and abilities acquired during the Bachelor's course should be further developed and improved in the Master's program. The specificity of the organization of independent work of Master's students consists in highly specialized profile training for future professional, scientific and research activities and implies a change in the nature of teacher-student interaction, as well as the use of new educational technologies, forms and methods of organization, according to which the teacher turns into an assistant. A master student becomes a subject of education, and his/her subject position is a factor of the educational process, and his/her

development is one of the main educational goals in the implementation of independent work [7, p. 1003].

It should be emphasized that independent work currently occupies no less than 70% of teaching time, as there is a transition from the model of "lifelong learning" to the concept of lifelong learning. Therefore, independent work turns into the main source and reserve of improving the quality of training of graduates, including Master's students. In the process of organizing independent work of Master's students in foreign language, teachers of the Department of Foreign Languages rely on the latest achievements of pedagogical thought. In this case, the definition of I.A. Zimneya is taken as a basis: "Independent work can be defined as a purposeful, internally motivated, structured by the subject in the totality of actions performed and corrected by him in the process and result of activity" [8, p. 255]. [8, c. 255].

Independent work of students can have different forms, depending on a number of factors. According to the place of carrying out independent work is divided into classroom work, which is carried out under the direct supervision of the teacher and extracurricular, which in turn has different forms, depending on the purpose, nature, discipline, volume of hours defined by the curriculum. Extracurricular independent work may include, for example, abstracting articles, separate sections of monographs; performing control works; writing thematic reports, essays and reports on problematic topics; annotating articles; performing research and creative assignments; project assignments, abstracting on a given topic, presentations. Taking into account all the variety of forms of tasks for extracurricular independent work, it is necessary at each stage to explain the goals of work, to control the understanding of these goals by master's students, gradually forming their ability to independently set the goal and define the tasks. When teaching foreign language to undergraduates the teachers of the department face the same difficulties as when working with bachelors, these are: different level of foreign language skills, a variety of psychological and physiological characteristics of students, insufficient number of hours, as well as the inability of undergraduates, students in general, to organize their learning activities.

However, it should be noted that independent work of Master students is more motivated, they are more conscious of their language training, firstly, due to the possibility of the need to conduct scientific research in foreign sources, Master students are aware of the importance of mastering a foreign language for the successful implementation of their research work, in addition, the possession of foreign languages increases the level of demand in the labour market. The final result of the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is determined by the target component - a master should see in a foreign language a means of obtaining and deepening knowledge in the direction of training, as well as a means of independent improvement of his/her qualification. One of the important tasks of a non-language university is to teach professional foreign language communication for further use of a foreign language in professional activity.

However, it is possible to master a foreign language practically, without being in the language environment, only under the condition of daily intensive training in its use.

In the course of independent work of master students, everyone uses the source of information depending on their capabilities and needs, which gives independent work an individualized character. Thus, the responsibility of students and, consequently, the motivation of learning increases. A master's student realises himself not as an object but as a subject of activity when he defines and sets himself goals and objectives, tries to achieve them, analyses them.

All this contributes to his positive motivation. Practice shows that the most demanded type of foreign language activity in the process of professionally oriented training of Master's students is reading aimed at information perception, and reading is increasingly acting as an independent type of speech activity. The main task of teaching reading at the stage of Master's degree is to develop the ability to extract information from the text in the framework of their research work, the initial stage of which is students' educational and research work. The main difference of reading instruction at the Master's stage is a greater degree of autonomy and individualization of learning. From the very beginning, Master's students should work with professionally relevant texts directly related to their future graduate work. In order to achieve this goal, an interdisciplinary approach, close contact with specialized departments and academic advisors of Master's students is of paramount importance.

As an example, we would like to cite our experience of professional contacts with the Department of Foreign Language, Faculty of Philology. At the first stage master students were acquainted with the goals and objectives of the foreign language program, required competences, forms of independent work and reporting on it. A lexico-grammatical test was conducted to determine the level of input knowledge. According to the results of the test, the planned material was corrected and reference books for independent repetition of problematic lexico-grammatical topics were indicated. Further master students chose for further work the directions agreed with the graduating department, in particular "Getting started in research", "The scientific community", "Finding a direction for your research", "Designing an experiment", "Describing a process. Evaluating the results of an experiment. Describing problems with an experiment Keeping a lab notebook".

Further work was organized according to the scheme: analysis of the linguistic material of the article

- compilation of the glossary - Annotation. The planned linguistic and speech material was considered within the framework of scientific texts in the areas chosen by master's students. Annotation of texts caused special difficulty, to facilitate the task a plan and a glossary for analyzing a scientific text using the means of logical connection were introduced. An effective type of independent work was the creation of theses in a foreign language on articles published by master's students. The final product of independent work on scientific articles on the subject of research work were oral presentations of master's students. It should be noted that the acquired experience gives master's students the skills to independently search for information in a foreign language, process, analyze, systematize, record and summarize the results obtained.

References:

1. Ignatieva A.V., Maksimtsov M.M. Research of control systems: a textbook for university students. - 2nd ed., revised. and additional - M.: UNITY-DANA: Law and Law, 2012.
2. Mishin V.M. Research of control systems: textbook for universities. - M.: UNITY-DANA, 2012.
3. Sadykova O.I. Theoretical and methodological foundations for the development of cognitive independence of students in the educational process of a technical university / O.I. Sadykova // Sat. scientific works of doctoral students, graduate students and applicants of psychological and pedagogical departments of TSPU named after. L.N. Tolstoy. - Tula: Publishing House TSPU im. L.N. Tolstoy, 2001. - pp. 109-113.
4. Kamenskaya L.S. On the issue of developing personal qualities of students necessary for autonomous learning activities in a foreign language // Autonomy in the practice of teaching foreign languages and cultures. - M., 2001. P. 39-48 (Tr./MSLU; issue 454).
5. Verbitsky A.A., Platonova T.A. Formation of cognitive and professional motivation of students. - M.: Education, 1986. - 178 p.
6. Organization of independent work of students in foreign languages at universities with non-linguistic specialties. Methodological recommendations for teachers. - M.: Moscow State Pedagogical Institute named after. M. Thorez, 1988. - 72 p.
7. Popova R.I. Independent work as a component of the training system for masters of pedagogical education in the field of life safety // Young scientist. - 2014. - No. 3. - P. 1002-1005.
8. Winter. Pedagogical psychology: a textbook for universities. - ed. 2nd, additional, correct. and processed - M.: Logos, 2001. - 384 p.